

Cultural Values and Innovation Performance of Employees in R & D Center of Foreign-Funded Enterprises in Suzhou High-Tech Zone

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Abstract

In recent years, Suzhou government has introduced a number of quality policies closely related to open innovation development and optimization of business environment, proposing that most of the policies are open to foreign-invested industries, foreign-invested enterprises and projects, allowing foreign-invested and domestic-invested entities to enjoy fair treatment and equal application. This paper reviews the concepts, dimensions, influencing factors and related studies of innovation performance, cultural values and cross-cultural competence. The theoretical model of this study is constructed by using the theoretical derivation method to propose the hypothesis of this paper. In the empirical research part, the questionnaire survey method and statistical analysis method are mainly used to conduct the study. Firstly, the questionnaire was determined by referring to the mature and widely accepted scales from abroad and making appropriate adjustments and modifications by combining with Chinese culture and characteristics. The questionnaire survey method was used to obtain empirical data from the employees of R&D centers of foreign-funded enterprises in Suzhou High-tech Zone. Subsequently, SPSS statistical software was used to analyze the data using statistical analysis methods.

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Introduction

Since 2020, the COVID-19 epidemic has dealt a huge blow to global cross-border investment and the world economy has been severely affected. The World Investment Report 2020, recently released by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, shows that global foreign direct investment will shrink significantly this year due to the impact of the epidemic, with the total amount expected to fall below US\$1 trillion, which will be 40% less than last year and the lowest level in the past 15 years. "This reduction of the negative list of foreign investment access demonstrates China's determination to adhere to a high level of openness to promote reform and development and resolutely oppose 'reverse globalization', which is conducive to further consensus building and jointly promoting the in-depth development of globalization." The level of openness has been increasing, and the confidence of foreign investors has been enhanced. Data show that in 2017-2019, against the backdrop of successive declines in global multinational investment, China attracted foreign investment amounting to US\$136.3 billion, US\$138.3 billion and US\$141.2 billion respectively, ranking second in the world. In May 2020, China actually used RMB 68.63 billion in foreign investment, up 7.5% year-on-year. Suzhou High-tech Zone is located in the west side of the ancient city of Suzhou, and is an important wing in the development pattern of "one body and two wings" of Suzhou city. Since the start of development, Suzhou High-tech Zone has always adhered to the principle of "people-oriented, comprehensive, coordinated and sustainable development", according to the development idea of gathering new industries, building a new urban area and establishing a new system, vigorously implementing the development strategy of giving equal importance to industrial development, urban construction and ecological protection, focusing on building high-standard infrastructure and high-grade environmental management system, so that the economic and social development of Suzhou High-tech Zone can be improved. The economic and social development has been sustained and rapid, and the economic indicators have always maintained a high growth rate of more than 20% per year, ranking among the top 53 national high-tech industrial development zones in China. At present, the region has introduced more than 1,000 foreign investment projects from more than 40 countries and regions, including 41 investment projects from global top 500 enterprises and 14 projects with investment of more than 100 million US dollars. The total investment of foreign investment projects exceeds 10 billion US dollars, with contracted foreign investment of 6.8 billion US dollars and recorded foreign investment of 4.1 billion US dollars, and the high-tech industry groups led by electronic information, precision machinery, medicine and fine chemicals, new materials and environmental protection have been formed. In the past 10 years, Suzhou High-tech Zone has grown from 52 square kilometers to 258 square kilometers, and has made great progress in finance and trade, transportation and information, science, education, culture and health, ecology and environment, especially in high-tech industries and open economy development. According to the industrial structure, more people are employed in the electronics and communication industry, accounting for 60% of the total number of employees, about 100,000 people; precision machinery industry accounts for 20% of the total number of employees, about 36,000 people; other industries such as biomedicine and fine chemical industry also account for 20% of the total number of employees. cultural conflicts in order to promote the innovation motivation and innovation results of R&D personnel, and then improve the innovation performance.

Problem Statement

Culture allows people from different cultures to have different needs and expectations, which increases the ambiguity and complexity of opinions in the workplace and can even lead to confusion and conflict in the management of foreign companies in China. At the same time, differences in cultural values make it difficult for employees from different cultural

backgrounds to understand or implement decision-making solutions and management systems differently (Audhesh et al. 2021). The diversity of cultural patterns determines the diversity of management patterns, and the diversity of management patterns brings great obstacles to the communication and cooperation between the managers of multinational companies and their partners in other countries. Good communication determines the quality of management, organizational performance and employee morale. Ignoring the racial superiority, mindset and perceptions of different nationalities shaped by cultural traditions, misunderstandings caused by different interpretations of cultural symbols, differences in cultural attitudes often lead to cultural conflicts, which in turn often lead to negative consequences such as resentment, extreme conservatism and irrational reflections. In multinational companies, the management obstacles caused by cross-cultural communication can affect the development of the company. The factors affecting performance have been the subject of research by management scholars. The core competence of a company lies in its innovation ability. In order to improve the core competitiveness of the enterprise, it is necessary to improve the innovation performance of the enterprise. With the rapid growth of multinational enterprises in China and the Suzhou municipal government's move to establish a globally influential science and technology innovation center, the issue of innovation performance of foreign-funded enterprises in Suzhou High-Tech Zone is gradually gaining attention. Due to the cross-cultural and transnational characteristics of foreign enterprises in Suzhou Hi-tech Zone, it is common to see cases of poor R&D effectiveness and closure of enterprises in China due to cultural conflicts or cultural misfit, and cross-cultural management has become a great challenge for foreign enterprises in Suzhou Hi-tech Zone. Dutch management psychologist Hofstede (1988) proposed a five-dimensional national cultural values theory, which divides cultural values at the national level into power distance, uncertainty avoidance, individualism and collectivism, rigid and flexible temperament, and long-term and short-term orientation. In recent years, scholars have found that even within the same national cultural values, the cultural values of organizations or individuals can vary greatly, and research on Hofstede's national cultural values theory has gradually expanded to include the organizational and individual levels. The deepest level of culture is values, which are the core of culture and are closely related to the ideals and beliefs shared by the group at a certain time. They address the question of "why do we do it", the orientation and purpose of human activity. It is the difference in values, the question of "why do" that ultimately determines "what" and "how" people do. Human activities are guided by values, and human activities and their results are, in the final analysis, the external expression of human values. Since values are the core of culture, we can also say that culture, in the end, refers to the values in a society, the opinions that people generally hold about ideals, beliefs, orientations, and attitudes. The difference between Chinese and Western cultures, between ancient and modern cultures, and between all cultures, is fundamentally a difference in values. The social role of culture is mainly the role of values. Any social group has its own culture, and there are values that are shared and believed by the members of the group. Any individual in society is a product of culture, and has its own values that it accepts and follows. In summary, the main issue studied in this paper is the innovation performance of employees in R&D centers of foreign-owned enterprises in Suzhou high-tech zone. First, the impact of multidimensional cultural values of employees in R&D centers on employees' innovation performance is explored in a cross-cultural context. Secondly, the moderating influence of cross-cultural competence on the five dimensions of employees' cultural values and innovation performance is investigated from the perspective of cross-cultural competence (Audhesh et al. 2021).

Research Question

Based on the problem statement, the research question will be formulated as follows. How to

determine the measurement dimensions of employees' cultural values in R&D centers of foreign companies?

Research Objective

Broadly speaking, this study aims to explore the relationship between employees' cultural values, employees' innovation performance, and cross-cultural competence in R&D centers of foreign companies in Suzhou High-tech Zone. Specifically, the research objectives are. To explore the measurement dimensions of employees' cultural values in R&D centers of foreign enterprises.

Scope of Study

This paper focuses on the R&D centers of foreign companies in Suzhou High-tech Zone of foreign companies in Suzhou High-tech Zone. In order to collect first-hand data and to ensure the limited data. The interviewees in this paper were targeted at the managers, junior managers and employees of the R&D centers of foreign companies in Suzhou High-tech Zone. The data is the factual basis of the study, and its authenticity and integrity are crucial.

Literature Review

Employee Innovation Performance

There is no unified concept of innovation performance in academia, and Hou Erxiu (2012) argues that there is a narrow sense of innovation performance and a broad sense of innovation performance. Most scholars believe that innovation performance and innovation outcomes have similarity. Innovation performance in the narrow sense refers to innovation capability and innovation results, focusing on results. freeman (1997) considers innovation performance in the narrow sense as the extent to which a company puts its invention patents into the market, and innovation performance is considered to be innovative only after the innovative technology is incorporated into new products and processes and achieves corporate benefits. Using the motivation-opportunity-competence theory of behavior as a general framework, Yueru Ma, Hongping Dai, & Xin Liang (2020) investigated the mechanism of feedback source heterogeneity on the innovation performance of knowledge employees by using 37 small and medium-sized emerging companies' supervisors and 327 knowledge employees as research subjects and testing the model with a hierarchical regression method. The results showed that feedback source heterogeneity directly and positively influenced the innovation performance of knowledge workers; performance climate and openness positively moderated the relationship between feedback source heterogeneity and innovation performance. The findings highlight that the relationship between feedback source heterogeneity and innovation performance is influenced by the work environment in which feedback is sought to be perceived. Yao Yanhong (2013), in her study of knowledge employees' innovation performance, classified knowledge employees' innovation performance into innovation actions and innovation effects. Innovation performance in a broad sense refers to the performance formed in the innovation process, focusing on the process. Ernst (2001) argues that innovation performance should be a dynamic process that contains three measures: patent content (quantified as the number of patents held and the conversion or citation rate of patents), R&D input, and new product release, which describe the entire stage from the concept of innovation to the introduction of new products into the market. The employee innovation performance studied in this paper views innovation performance as an outcome variable from a narrow perspective. This paper agrees more with Yao Yanhong's view on innovation performance, which divides innovation performance into two dimensions: behavior and outcome. Innovation performance is studied from the perspective of outcome.

Measurement of Employee Innovation Performance

Western scholars' measurement of employees' innovative performance is mainly based on Scott and Janssen's scale. Scott and Bruce (1994) developed an employee innovative behavior scale with 6 questions, based on Kanter's (1988) research on innovation, which was rated and measured by employees' immediate supervisors. Janssen (2001) designed an innovative performance scale based on Scott and Bruce's Individual Innovation Behavior Scale, designed the Innovation Performance Scale, which is designed with nine questions and includes three dimensions: idea generation, idea promotion, and realization of innovative ideas, and is assessed by managers on employees. Latif (2017), in his study on the interaction between individual innovation performance and reputation, based on Scott and Bruce's Individual Innovation Behavior Scale Behavior Scale and Janssen's Employee Innovation Performance Scale, Latif (2017) designed a 10-item innovation performance questionnaire. The research on innovation performance scale by Chinese scholars is also based on Scott and Janssen's scale. For example, Han Yi (2007) studied the structure of employee performance and classified employee performance into task performance, relationship performance, learning performance and innovation performance. In the measurement of innovation performance and borrowed from Janssen's innovation performance scale, the innovation performance questionnaire was developed in three aspects: innovation desire, innovation action, and innovation outcome. Based on Scott's scale, Jingji Wu used back-translation method to translate the scale into Chinese culture and modified it appropriately to form a 7-item innovative behavior scale for employees to self-assess their innovative behavior performance. Liu, Yun and Shi, Jintao (2009), in their study on the interaction effect of organizational innovation climate and motivational preferences on employees' innovation behavior, developed an employee innovation behavior questionnaire based on Scott's scale and Wu, Jingji's study. Yao Yanhong (2013), in her study of knowledge employees' innovation performance, classified knowledge employees' innovation performance into innovation actions and innovation effects, and developed an innovation performance scale based on the dimensions of innovation performance. In this paper, we believe that innovation performance is a result-oriented variable, so we agree more with Yao Yanhong's view, which mainly measures the behavior and effect of innovation.

Influencing factors of employee innovation performance

There are many factors that affect employee innovation performance, Hammond (2011) pointed out that individual factors, job characteristics, and environmental factors all affect innovation. Zheng Ye (2017) categorized the factors influencing innovation performance into three levels of factors: individual, organizational or team, and social. Erli Ma (2015) classified the factors affecting individual innovation performance into individual factors and organizational contextual factors. In this paper, we will briefly review the factors affecting individual innovation performance from two aspects: individual factors and organizational context. First, the influence of individual level on employees' innovation performance. Wanqing (2012) concluded that innovation intention has a positive impact on employee innovation performance through employee knowledge absorption ability and knowledge diffusion path. Zhang, J. (2014) concluded that pre-pregnant personality significantly and positively affects employee innovation performance, that employees' feedback seeking behavior plays a fully mediating role, and that supervisors' support for innovation can promote employee innovation. Huang and Liang (2015) studied supervisors and their 355 subordinates in 73 work teams in Chinese companies and concluded that in terms of individual-level effects, organizational self-esteem mediates between job well-being and innovation performance, and job well-being affects innovation performance by influencing organizational self-esteem. Fan (2016) Individuals' interactive memory system significantly

affects individual innovation performance, where creative self-efficacy positively mediates the relationship between interactive memory systems and individual innovation performance (Audhesh et al. 2021).

Methodology

This paper is divided into two major parts: theoretical research and empirical research. The theoretical research part mainly adopts the textual analysis method, literature review method, and theoretical deduction method to conduct the research. The text analysis method is an objective and systematic description of literature and texts. In this paper, based on the website text and Chinese and English references, the selected topic of this paper is proposed through the analysis of this paper. Checking relevant domestic and foreign theses, journal literature, master's and doctoral dissertations, etc., the literature review method is used to extract the research lineage and content of multidimensionality of cultural values, employee innovation performance, and cross-cultural competence, etc. The literature is categorized and reviewed, and the deficiencies in the existing research are found. Based on the existing research base, this paper uses the theoretical derivation method to propose the research hypothesis of this paper and construct the theoretical model of this study. In the empirical research part, the questionnaire survey method and statistical analysis method are mainly used to conduct the study. Firstly, the questionnaire is determined by referring to the mature and widely accepted scales from abroad, and making appropriate adjustments and modifications by combining with Chinese culture and characteristics. The questionnaire survey method was used to obtain empirical data from the employees of R&D centers of foreign-funded enterprises in Suzhou High-tech Zone.

Measurement of variables

Dimensions of employees' cultural values

In this paper, we refer to Dorfman and Howell's (1988) individual cultural values scale and Jinwei Li's (2012) scale to investigate the five dimensions of employees' power distance, uncertainty avoidance, collective individualism orientation, flexible-rigid orientation, and long-term-short-term orientation cultural values, and the proposed employee cultural values scale is shown in Table 3-1 below.

Table3- 1 Dimensional scale of employees' cultural values

Dimension	NO.	Title item
C1 Low power distance	1	C1-1 I think leaders should consult other colleagues when making decisions
	2	C1-2 I have a good working relationship with my immediate supervisor
	3	C1-3 I am afraid to express my dissatisfaction with my supervisor (reverse scoring)
	4	C1-4 I am afraid of arguing with my leader about work-related issues (reverse scoring)
C2 Weak uncertainty avoidance	5	C2-1 I think there should be reasonable room for mistakes in R&D
	6	C2-2 I think breaking the company system can be forgiven if it is in the best interest of the company
	7	C2-3 Employees must strictly follow company rules and regulations (reverse scoring)
	8	C2-4 I prefer fixed, system-defined work content and processes (reverse scoring)
C3 Collectivism	9	C3-1 I think collective innovation is more important than individual innovation
	10	C3-2 I like to discuss solutions to problems collectively
	11	C3-3 I think that major decisions should be made by collective discussion
	12	C3-4 I believe that overall company goals should be considered before pursuing my own small goals
C4 Soft culture	13	C4-1 I prefer to resolve conflicts through negotiation rather than forceful means
	14	C4-2 I prefer a comfortable and flexible office environment to a stressful work environment

	15	C4-3 I like to work for a reputable and fulfilling company or organization
	16	C4-4 I can achieve a work-life balance
C5 Long-term Orientation	17	C5-1 I will research a new area of work, even if this area has not been studied yet
	18	C5-2 I believe that efforts at work should be rewarded immediately (reverse scoring)
	19	C5-3 I will learn for long-term development
	20	C5-4 I think consistent effort is the most reliable way to achieve good results

The dimension scale of employee cultural values has a total of 20 questions, among which questions 1-4 correspond to the cultural values of power distance, questions 5-8 correspond to the cultural values of uncertainty avoidance, questions 9-12 correspond to the cultural values of collectivism, questions 13-16 correspond to the cultural values of flexibility and questions 17-20 correspond to the cultural values of long-term orientation. The items were scored on a five-level Likert scale, with items 3, 4, 7, 8 and 18 being scored in the reverse direction. The higher the average score of the four items of power distance, the more inclined the employees are to the cultural values of low power distance. The higher the average score of the four items of uncertainty avoidance is, the more inclined the employees are to the weak uncertainty avoidance cultural values. The higher the average score of the four items of collectivism, the more inclined the employees are to collectivist cultural values. The higher the average score of the four items of flexible culture, the more inclined the employees are to the value of flexible culture. The higher the average score of the four items of long-term orientation, the more inclined the employees are to long-term orientation cultural values.

Employee innovation performance

The dependent variable of this paper is employee innovation performance, which is mainly viewed from the results of innovation. Therefore, the innovation performance questionnaire developed by Yao Yanhong (2013) of Hunan University is used to divide innovation performance into innovation action and innovation effect. Innovative actions include innovative ideas, adopting new technologies or methods, and developing know-how. Innovation effect includes innovation achievement, innovation application and innovation effect. The innovation performance scale to be adopted in this paper is shown in Table 3-3 below. The scale has a total of 6 questions, which are scored by the five-level Likert scale. The average score of the six questions represents the level of innovation performance of employees, and the larger the average score, the better the innovation performance of employees.

Table3- 2 Employee Innovation Performance Scale

The dimension		NO.	Item
P1 Innovative Action	Innovative ideas	1	P1-1 In my work, I can provide innovative ideas to improve technology and process
	Adopt new technology	2	P1-2 In my work, I can use new methods and technologies to reduce costs and increase output
	Conclusion the trick	3	P1-3 In my work, I can summarize feasible new working methods to improve work efficiency
P2 Innovation Effect	Innovations	4	P2-1 The new products and technologies I develop and improve are of higher quality
	Innovative applications	5	P2-2 The new products and technologies I developed and improved have been applied to many workplaces
	Innovation results	6	P2-3 The new products and technologies I developed and improved were well received by customers

Questionnaire pre-test

The questionnaire in this paper is mainly composed of four parts, namely, the basic information of the survey object, the scale of cultural values, the scale of cross-cultural

competence, and the scale of employee innovation performance. Each scale adopts the Richter 5-point scoring method, that is, "1" means "very inconsistent", "5" means "very consistent", and the reverse scoring items are scored in reverse. Please refer to the attachment for the survey questionnaire. This pre-survey is mainly distributed to employees of 10 R&D centers of foreign enterprises in Suzhou High-tech Zone. A total of 50 questionnaires were distributed and 48 were recovered, with a recovery rate of 96%. Incomplete questionnaires were deleted, and 44 valid questionnaires were finally pre-investigated, with an effective rate of 88%.

Table3- 3 Reliability results of the pre-survey questionnaire (n=44)

Scale	Cronbach ss coefficient
Employee Cultural Values Scale	0.907
Employee Innovation Performance Scale	0.942
Staff Intercultural Competence Scale	0.957

Judging from the Klongbach coefficient in Table 3-5, the meter table adopted in this article has a good degree of reliability, so a pre-adjustment questionnaire can be used for formal investigation.

Data Collection Process

In order to ensure the smooth distribution of questionnaires, as well as the quality of the recovered questionnaires. On November 1 2021 invited suzhou high-tech zone management committee, deputy director of the Japan research arranged a symposium, invited the Fujitsu multimedia components (suzhou) co., LTD, suzhou industrial park, guosen ark software technology co., LTD., than o 'shea gases (suzhou) co., LTD., lilly pharmaceutical (suzhou) co., LTD., black & decker (suzhou) power tools co., LTD. Representatives from 10 companies, including Renesas Semiconductor (Suzhou) Co., LTD., Shaogen Frogl Glue Injection Technology (Suzhou Industrial Park) Co., LTD., Honeywell Aero Engine (Suzhou) Co., LTD., Nova Chemical (Suzhou) Co., LTD., and Takemoto Oil (Suzhou) Co., LTD., attended the meeting. At the symposium, the research topic of "The relationship between cross-cultural competence, cultural values and innovation performance of R&D centers" was discussed. In the seminar, I introduced the purpose of this research, the content of the research, the design of the questionnaire and the rules of filling in the questionnaire. At the same time, I invited them to randomly distribute the questionnaire to the R&D staff of the enterprise, and collect the questionnaire one week later. A total of 400 questionnaires were distributed and 396 questionnaires were recovered, with a recovery rate of 99%, through the investigation of 10 R&D centers of foreign enterprises in Suzhou High-tech Zone. There were 82 invalid questionnaires with incomplete content, and 314 valid samples were finally obtained, with an effective rate of 79.29%.

Finding

Profile of the Respondent

Suzhou High-tech Zone, the full name of Suzhou High-tech Industrial Development Zone. It is located in the west of Suzhou Ancient City, east of the Beijing-Hangzhou Grand Canal, south of Wuzhong District, north of Xiangcheng District, west to Taihu Lake. The regional population is 774,800, including 587,800 permanent residents, 182,000 temporary residents and 5,000 foreigners. Suzhou Industrial Park is a "test field" of reform and opening up, a successful example of innovative cooperation, and a modern industrial new town that started from scratch but has added a heavy color to the construction of China's development zones. Suzhou High-tech Zone has first-class industrial supporting services and excellent ecological innovation vitality. Its strong support and all-round guarantee for foreign-funded enterprises have made fruitful achievements in their continuous investment in Suzhou. At present, the

high-tech zone is to "2 + 6 + X" modern industry system and focus on developing a new generation of information technology, medical equipment and biological medicine, high-end manufacturing, new energy, integrated circuits, digital economy, such as industry, formed a relatively complete industrial ecosystem, to the development of foreign project provides a high-quality business environment. The settlement of these high-quality projects will also help the high-tech zone extend the upstream and downstream industrial chain and promote the faster development of various industries. By the end of 2021, nearly 1,800 foreign enterprises had been introduced to the high-tech zone, including 645 Japanese enterprises and nearly 400 European and American enterprises. Fujitsu Multimedia Components (Suzhou) Co., LTD., Guosen Ark Software Technology Co., LTD., Biosi Gas (Suzhou) Co., LTD., Eli Lilly (Suzhou) Pharmaceutical Co., LTD., Black & Decker (Suzhou) Power Tools Co., LTD., Renesas semiconductor (suzhou) co., LTD., XiaoGenFu rogge injecting technology (suzhou industrial park) co., LTD., honeywell aerospace engine (suzhou) co., LTD., nova chemical (suzhou) co., LTD., bamboo this grease (suzhou) co., LTD are a representative of foreign company in suzhou high-tech zone, and these enterprises to develop strong, relying on superior in suzhou high-tech zone policy, Integrating into the R&D industry ecosystem of the high-tech zone, it has made great contributions to scientific and technological innovation, and has recruited and trained many local scientific research talents in China. With the clear goal of building a world-class high-tech industrial park, keen park personnel also see their own current industrial level is not high enough, the core competitiveness is not strong enough, growth momentum is not enough and other problems. With the rise of the global industrial division of labor adjustment wave in recent years, the park faces the reality, enhances the development concentration with transformation efforts, establishes the industrial transformation and upgrading supervision platform, vigorously develops intelligent manufacturing, deepens the integration pilot of industrialization and informatization, and gives guidance to the industrial transformation from the government level. With policy guidance, real investment and every effort to make room for development, manufacturing enterprises in the park are accelerating to the high-end. In the past, the park relied more on the introduction of technology to promote industrial development, taking the "road of latecomer" characterized by learning and imitation. Standing at the new starting point of the 40th anniversary of reform and opening up and the key stage of the economic transition to high-quality development, the park has the foundation and conditions to catch up with the industrial development by relying on independent innovation, and set out a "first mover" characterized by innovation. "At present, the park has joined the ranks of the Ministry of Science and Technology in building world-class high-tech parks. This is a new starting point and a new platform for us to start our reform and take a new step in opening up. A mature and sound innovation nurturing system is the key to transforming the driving forces of development and building a new model of development that is mainly led and supported by innovation. Research and development of leading technology, transformation of original achievements, is the top priority of regional industrial development. At present, on the one hand, the park vigorously cultivates and strengthens the innovative and entrepreneurial enterprise cluster. By supporting enterprises to carry out independent innovation, the park has formed a trend of "four 90% enterprises" in scientific research institutions, scientific and technological personnel, R&D investment and scientific and technological achievements, and successfully gathered more than 4,000 scientific and technologically innovative enterprises and 875 national high-tech enterprises. In the future, the Park will shoulder the responsibility and mission of building a world-class high-tech park, take scientific and technological innovation as the core strategy of regional development and an important starting point of transformation and upgrading, open up the channel for the transformation of scientific and technological achievements, accelerate the improvement of the market-oriented mechanism

for the transformation of achievements, and actively build a carrier of open and shared cross-border collaborative innovation. We will promote the transformation of decentralized innovation into industrial chain innovation and systematic innovation, so that more "technological bonsai" will become "industrial scenery". In such a big era of development, it is very important for Suzhou HIGH-TECH Zone Foreign Enterprise R&D Center to focus on the training of talents, the high-quality of talents, and accelerate the integration of Chinese and foreign talents to create the future together with wisdom. Therefore, this paper focuses on clarifying the relationship between cultural values, cross-cultural competence and innovation performance of employees in R&D centers of foreign companies, which is of great significance for talents to exert their maximum motivation.

Demographic analysis

Through questionnaire analysis, 226 Chinese employees and 88 non-Chinese employees were surveyed. In the survey of the size of foreign R&D centers, 51.7% of the teams belong to R&D centers with more than 21 members. In the survey of non-Chinese employees in multinational teams, 47.8% of R&D centers have 5 or less non-Chinese employees, and 28.7% of R&D centers have 21 or more non-Chinese employees, indicating that the R&D combination of small team and large team is preferred in the selection of R&D center size. In the survey of gender, 242 were male, accounting for 77.1%, indicating a high proportion of male employees in R&D centers. In the age survey, it is found that most R&D employees are 26-30 years old, accounting for 55.4%. In the survey of education level, there were 12 doctoral samples; There are 166 samples for master degree and 132 samples for undergraduate degree, indicating that the R&D center is mainly staffed by employees with master degree. In terms of working years, the majority of employees are those who have worked for 5 years or less. In the survey of technical titles, all the employees in the R&D center have technical titles, and 23 of them have junior titles, accounting for 7.3%; 260 intermediate titles, accounting for 82.8%; 19, accounting for 6.1%; There are 12 people with senior professional titles, accounting for 3.8%. The research and development personnel of foreign enterprises are all technical personnel with certain technical titles, among which the number of employees with intermediate titles is the largest. See Table 4-1 for details:

Table4- 1 Distribution of basic Information of Survey Subjects (n=314)

Sample characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Nationality	Chinese	226	71.97
	Non-chinese nationality	88	28.03
Scale of research and development center	5 or less	42	14.1
	6-10	66	22.1
	11-20	40	12.1
	21 or more	166	51.7
Number of non-Chinese employees in multinational team	5 or less	150	47.8
	6-10	46	14.6
	11-20	28	8.9
	21 or more	90	28.7
Gender	Male	242	77.1
	Female	72	22.9
Age	Age 25 and under	52	16.6
	26-30	174	55.4
	31-35	44	14.0
	36-40	28	8.9
	Age 41 and older	16	5.1
Education level	Dr.	12	3.8
	Master	166	52.9
	Undergraduate	132	42.0
	Other	4	1.3
Working fixed number of year	1 year or less	68	21.7
	2 to 3 years	70	22.3

	4-5 years	72	22.9
	6-10 years	56	17.8
	11 years and above	48	15.3
Technical titles	No	0	0
	Primary title	23	7.3
	Intermediate title	260	82.8
	Subtropical high title	19	6.1
	Is the title	12	3.8

Influence of control variables on employee innovation performance

In order to consider the influence of control variables on the dependent variable, this section discusses the influence of control variables on the dependent variable employee innovation performance. Independent sample T test or one-way ANOVA analysis were performed according to the category of variables. The control variables tested are nationality, gender, age, working years, education level, technical title, multinational team size, and the number of non-national employees in the team. The significance level of independent sample T test was 0.267. Independent sample T test was performed for gender, and the significance level of independent sample T test was 0.628. One-way analysis of variance was performed for education level, and the significance level of ANOVA analysis was 0.834. One-way analysis of variance was performed for technical titles, and the significance level of ANOVA was 0.301. One-way analysis of variance was performed for the size of the multinational team, and the significance level of ANOVA was 0.268. The number of non-native employees in different multinational teams was analyzed by one-way analysis of variance, and the significance level of ANOVA analysis was 0.758. It can be seen that the significance levels of the above tests are all greater than 0.05. Therefore, different nationalities, gender, education level, technical titles, multinational team size, and number of non-native employees in the team have no significant impact on the innovation performance of employees, and the specific research process will not be detailed. Only results with significant differences are discussed below. According to the empirical results, different ages and working years have a significant impact on the innovation performance of employees. Therefore, in the subsequent main effect test and moderating effect test, control variables need to be controlled and included in the regression equation.

Table4- 2 Comparison results of mean value of innovation performance of employees in different age groups

Variable	The average	The standard deviation	Standard error of	95% confidence interval for the mean		The minimum value	The maximum
				lower limit	Ceiling		
Age 25 and under	26	3.9231	0.82628	0.16205	3.5893	4.2568	2.83
Age 26 to 30	87	3.5134	0.74805	0.08020	3.3540	3.6728	1.83
Age 31-35	22	3.5227	0.81047	0.17279	3.1634	3.8821	1.33
Age 36-40	14	4.0000	0.75674	0.20225	3.5631	4.4369	2.33
Age 41 and older	8	4.0417	0.50982	0.18025	3.6154	4.4679	3.33
A total of	157	3.6529	0.78082	0.06232	3.5298	3.7760	1.33

In order to analyze and compare the strong and weak relationship between the influence of different age groups on innovation performance, the intra-group comparative mean analysis was conducted. The results are shown in Table 4-3. It can be seen that employees over 41

years old have the best innovation performance.

Influence of cultural values on employee innovation performance

Correlation analysis mainly verifies the correlation coefficient between variables. The closer the absolute value of the correlation coefficient is to 1, the higher the degree of correlation between variables. Correlation analysis must be carried out before moderating effect, otherwise the results of moderating effect analysis will be meaningless. In this paper, Pearson correlation analysis of variables was performed by SPSS. The results of the correlation between the five dimensions of cultural values and employee innovation performance are shown in Tables 4-6. According to the regression data of each cultural value dimension on innovation performance in the last column of the table, each cultural value dimension (C1 low power distance cultural value, C2 weak uncertainty avoidance cultural value, C3 collectivist cultural value, C4 flexible cultural value, The significance (two-tailed) between C5 long-term oriented cultural values) and employee innovation performance is significant at 0.01 level, and the correlation of all variables is significant, which passes the correlation test.

Conclusion

In the empirical part of this paper, it is concluded that the multi-dimension of employee cultural values has a significant impact on employee innovation performance. Low power distance cultural values, weak uncertainty avoidance cultural values, collectivism cultural values, flexible cultural values and long-term orientation cultural values all have a significant positive impact on employee innovation performance (Audhesh et al. 2021). However, in foreign-funded enterprises in Suzhou High-tech Zone, employees come from different countries and regions and have different cultural backgrounds. Therefore, it is difficult to integrate cultures in cross-cultural management, and more negative effects are caused by cross-cultural conflicts. In this paper, the management suggestions for foreign-funded enterprises in Suzhou High-tech Zone are to promote cross-cultural integration among employees with different cultural backgrounds. To promote cultural integration, we need to pay attention to the following points: 1. Cultural integration should respect the cultures of various countries. To reduce cross-cultural conflicts, we need to respect the cultures of various countries, correctly understand the cultures of various countries, correctly understand the cultural values of employees, and recognize and respect the cultural differences and diversity of various countries, so as to effectively avoid cultural value conflicts. In the study of solving cross-cultural conflicts, Harris & Moran (1987) gave three solutions to solve cultural conflicts, which can be selected and applied by enterprises according to their internal cultural characteristics. The third method is collaboration (cultural integration). In this paper, it is suggested that enterprises should adopt a collaborative way to create a unified corporate collaborative culture. On the basis of respecting the cultural background of each member, we respect and understand each other, and form a collaborative culture of the enterprise. Compared with ling, the two kinds of cross-cultural conflict and compromise solution, collaborative approach can make the enterprise culture has more stability, the method of seeking common ground while putting aside differences can neither deny a kind of culture, also won't by a kind of culture as the dominant, but in considering cultural values on the basis of the integration and optimization of whole operation has more obvious advantage for enterprises. 2. Form correct cultural values and view on cultural integration Culture is not static. Only through cultural integration and development, absorbing strengths and avoiding weaknesses, can we achieve greater development. In the process of cultural integration, we must have corrected cultural values and views of cultural integration. To form a collaborative culture, we must know what kind of culture the enterprise needs. It is necessary to have a correct view of cultural integration, establish an open mind, improve the understanding of

different cultural values, hold a tolerant attitude towards cultural integration, eliminate cultural stereotypes, prevent ethnocentrism, and improve the dual cultural identity and cultural intelligence of employees. In the process of cultural integration, attention should be paid to the role of people, people-oriented, concerned about the needs of employees, attach importance to the value of people, and improve the cross-cultural ability of employees (Audhesh et al. 2021)

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